

PJBL (PROJECT BASE LEARNING) METHOD IN THE ARABIC LANGUAGE TEACHING MODULE ININDEPENDENT CURRICULUM

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Abstract: This research aims to analyze the effectiveness of implementing the Project Based Learning (PJBL) method in the Arabic language teaching module in the Independent Curriculum at the junior and senior high school levels in Semarang City. PJBL is a student-centered learning method, where they are involved in projects that are relevant to real-life contexts, to improve language skills and understanding of Arabic culture. This research uses a mixed approach with qualitative and quantitative methods. Data was collected through questionnaires, interviews, observations and document analysis from 10 schools (5 junior high schools and 5 high schools) with a total of 250 students and 15 teachers. The results of the research show that the implementation of PJBL significantly improves students' Arabic language skills, especially in speaking and writing. . In addition, students' learning motivation increases because they feel more involved and enthusiastic in the learning process. Collaboration and problem-solving skills have also improved, with students working effectively in groups to complete their projects. However, several challenges are faced, such as limited resources and teacher readiness in designing projects that suit students' level of understanding. Overall, the PJBL method has proven to be effective in improving the quality of Arabic language learning in Semarang City, in line with the principles of the Independent Curriculum which emphasizes integrated learning. Independent and creative. Recommendations from this research include the need for more intensive teacher training, provision of adequate infrastructure, as well as the development of PJBL- based teaching modules that are tiered according to students' education level.

Keywords: PJBL (Project Base Learning), Arabic Teaching Module, Independent Learning Curriculum.

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Introduction

The Independent Curriculum is a new curriculum implemented in Indonesia (Sholeh et al., 2024). This curriculum gives educators the freedom to create quality learning that suits the needs and learning environment of students. The Merdeka Curriculum aims to simplify the previous curriculum which seemed complicated and could not meet the competency achievements of students (Aji, 2023). One of the advantages of the Merdeka Curriculum is that it provides greater freedom to educational units in developing curriculum and implementing learning. Implementation of the Merdeka Curriculum has started in 2022, and a number of schools in various regions have implemented it. The aim of the Merdeka Belajar Curriculum is to simplify the previous curriculum which seemed complicated and could not meet the competency achievements of students. In addition. This curriculum aims to provide greater freedom to

educational units in developing curriculum and implementing learning (Wirawan et al., 2024). The Independent Curriculum also aims to make schools and regional governments have the authority to manage their own education in accordance with the conditions in their region. Apart from that, another aim is to accelerate achieving national education goals, preparing for global challenges in the era of revolution 4.0, and strengthening character education through the Pancasila Student Profile (Astuti & Suastra, 2024). The Independent Learning Curriculum helps develop student competency by providing greater freedom to educational units in developing curriculum and implementing learning. This curriculum also provides flexibility for educators and supports teaching tools and training materials to develop educational unit curricula and implement quality learning. , The Merdeka Curriculum focuses more on essential material and the development of students' competencies in each phase, so that the learning process is expected to be more in-depth, meaningful, less rushed and fun

(Marthawati & Setyo, 2024). The Merdeka Curriculum also aims to accelerate the achievement of national education goals, preparing for global challenges.

The Merdeka Curriculum emphasizes developing student competencies, and learning outcomes are one way to measure the achievement of these competencies (Aji, 2023). The Merdeka Curriculum Learning Outcomes are designed to strengthen the focus of learning on essential material such as literacy and numeracy, as well as develop students' abilities or competencies, the Independent Curriculum also provides greater freedom to educational units, Teaching modules are very important in the Independent Learning Curriculum because teaching modules can help educators in developing more meaningful and effective learning, Teaching modules are designed to make it easier for educators to design learning that suit the learning needs and interests of students. Teaching modules can also help students understand learning material better and more deeply. Apart from that, teaching modules can help educators measure students' competency achievements.

A good teaching module must meet the essential criteria, be interesting, meaningful and challenging, relevant and contextual, and sustainable, consider the phase or stage of student development, consider what will be learned with learning objectives, and be based on long-term development (Munfaati et al., 2022). Thus, the teaching module can help develop students' competencies more optimally and in accordance with students' learning needs and interests.

One of the approaches used in this curriculum is Project-Based Learning (PJBL) or project-based learning. PJBL is a learning method that emphasizes active and collaborative learning experiences, where students learn through projects or assignments that are challenging and relevant to real life (Komara et al., 2023). In the context of Arabic language learning, the development of PJBL-based teaching modules aims to improve students' ability to communicate effectively in Arabic. This teaching module is designed to enable students to learn Arabic through projects or assignments that are challenging and relevant to real life, such as making presentations, creating videos, or writing essays in Arabic. Thus, students can develop their Arabic language skills more effectively and have fun.

The Independent Curriculum's flexibility requires innovative teaching methods and tools to ensure its objectives are achieved, particularly in fostering student competencies and preparing for global challenges. Developing PJBL-based teaching modules in Arabic language learning addresses the need for meaningful, contextual, and effective learning methods that align with the curriculum's focus on essential skills and character development. This research contributes to the development of evidence-based teaching modules that integrate PJBL to enhance Arabic language learning outcomes, especially in communication skills. It also provides practical insights for educators to implement student-centered learning approaches that align with the Independent Curriculum's objectives and principles.

Research Method

This research uses quantitative and qualitative methods with a case study approach. Data is collected through, Questionnaires and interviews with students and teachers at junior and senior high

schools who implement PJBL in Arabic language learning. Direct observation in class to see the PJBL implementation process, and document analysis of teaching modules and student project results. The research sample consisted of 5 junior high schools and 5 high schools in Semarang City, with a total of 250 students and 15 teachers as respondents.

The PJBL (Project Based Learning) method is a project-based learning method that prioritizes students' active involvement in the learning process through real and contextual projects (Hussein et al., 2024). In the context of the Arabic Language Teaching Module in the Independent Curriculum, the PJBL method can be applied in the following ways.

First, the stages of PPA in Arabic are usually carried out in several stages, such as: (a) project determination, students are invited to choose a topic or problem that is relevant to Arabic, for example creating a poster in Arabic, producing a video of an Arabic conversation, or creating an Arabic visual dictionary, (b) project planning, together with the teacher, students plan the steps in working on the project, including the resources needed and the deadline, (c) project implementation: Students work independently or in groups to complete the project, while applying the Arabic language skills they have learned, (d) presentation of results: Project results are presented in Arabic, which encourages students to use the language actively and creatively, (e) reflection and evaluation: Teachers and students jointly evaluate project results, identify strengths and weaknesses, and provide feedback for future improvements.

Second, the implementation of PJBL in the Arabic Language Teaching Module, which can be applied to various topics in the Arabic language teaching module, such as: (a) vocabulary and grammar: Students can develop projects to create interactive learning media, such as vocabulary cards, short stories, or minibooks that focus on specific grammar, (b) communication skills: Projects involving everyday conversations in Arabic can practice speaking, listening, writing and reading skills. For example, making a log in Arabic that reviews Arab culture, (c) understanding Arabic culture: Students can work on research projects on culture and traditions in Arabic-speaking countries, which are then presented in Arabic.

Discussion

The learning model using problem based learning (PBL) is a student center learning model (Asri et al., 2024). The PBL learning process presents real problems as a learning resource so that students can solve problems and find solutions. Problem-based learning is student-centered learning that is in accordance with the principles of constructivism (Sagatbek et al., 2024). The principle of constructivism is that students can build their knowledge through the problems they are given. The opinion above is also supported by Mudrikah (2021) who explain in their research "Problem-based learning (PBL) is considered a student-centered instruction approach in which inspired students to apply critical thinking through simulated problems in order to study complicated multifaceted, and practical problems that may or may not have standard answers".

Zhao (2024) explain that PBL is a pedagogical approach that allows students to learn while being actively involved in solving problems. Students are given the opportunity to solve problems in a collaborative setting among students, create models for learning, and form independent learning habits through practice and reflection

(Nicholus et al., 2023). Students are actively involved in learning so that it can progress well. In PBL, the problems used are problems that are unclear or problems that have not yet been resolved. With these problems still floating around, students are expected to be able to deepen and look for the main points of the problem so that they can find a solution (Gnaldi et al., 2020). (da Fonsêca Barros & Penna, 2023) states that PBL is a model that is built based on a real problem in life and is still unstructured, unclear and has not been identified, making it a confusing situation with a number of other problems. The application of the PBL model so that students are able to increase understanding by searching, exploring information by determining and recognizing problems and being able to search solutions and conclude based on what they have analyzed. Graaff (2003: 1) explains that PBL is a learning model where educational resources come from a problem, the type of problem used adapts to the material and is usually a problem in everyday life (Magdalena et al., 2023).

Problems that exist in life are introduced and studied so that students understand the problem and are able to know how to solve it. The learning experience gained is very important, where experience plays a role in building knowledge and understanding concepts in life regarding style, rights and obligations as well as natural resources. Understanding of the material is presented in the form of problems so that students can think based on the experiences they have had to form their thinking patterns so that the problems given can be solved.

As stated by Ajai, Dos Santos (2021) "PBL as an instructional strategy based on constructivism, is the concept that learners construct their own understanding by relating concrete experience to existing knowledge where the process of collaboration and reflection are involved". Learning does not only require students to get high grades in learning, but learning is a place for students to be able to solve the problems they face. Learning using PBL encourages students to understand problems and be able to provide examples of real problems. Kodariyati & Astuti (2016: 4) explain that PBL is a problem-based learning model that can help students' understanding of subject matter, besides that PBL allows students' thinking skills to develop further.

Students are directed to be able to think systematically and analyze their surroundings and build an understanding of the real problems around them. Tanna (2022) explains, problem-based learning is learning that uses a student-centered approach 16 which is arranged like a problem situation in the real world. Students are expected to be able to develop their way of thinking based on what they experience and analyze it so they can determine the right steps for them to take.

Agrees with Usanmaz & Basal, (2023) who explain that PBL provides real experiences that encourage active learning, supports knowledge construction, and naturally integrates school learning and real life, and also PBL provides a positive influence on creative thinking, problem solving ,academic achievement, attitudes, and scientific processes. (Tanna et al., 2022) students are directed to be able to think systematically and analyze their surroundings and build an understanding of the real problems around them. (Usanmaz & Basal, 2023) explains, problem-based learning is learning that uses a student-centered approach 16 which is arranged like a problem situation in the real world.

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PBL learning requires students to develop themselves through self-learning experiences from problems. PBL learning is constructivist learning or building students' understanding. (Jumhur et al., 2024) explains "the underpinning philosophy of PBL is that learning can be considered a "constructive, self-directed, collaborative and contextual" activity". The meaning of the problem-based learning philosophy is that learning can be considered as an activity that builds knowledge, is independent, trains collaboration and cooperation and is contextual.

In line with the opinion above (Nurhuda et al., 2023) explains that problem-based learning (PBL) is based on constructivist theory which has the following characteristics: (1) students can gain understanding of the environment by interacting. Problems are used as a learning resource to become a learning reference and to achieve the expected learning objectives from the material, (2) students receive stimulation from problems directly which causes students' interest in learning. The stimulation received by students causes the atmosphere to look for ways to reduce anxiety or discomfort so that students can find ways to get out of this atmosphere, (3) learning and experience occur through a collaborative process between experience and learning. This means that the knowledge that students have is the result of what they have obtained from the learning and experiences they have undergone. PBL learning also requires collaboration between students to get optimal results. Learning with PBL will also influence students' cooperative attitudes. Groups that work together well will have more satisfying results than groups that lack cooperation.

Research Result

The research results show that the implementation of PJBL significantly improves students' Arabic language skills, especially in speaking and writing skills. Projects such as creating conversation videos in Arabic, developing mini dictionaries, and presentations in Arabic give students the opportunity to actively practice the language. Middle School: Students experience significant improvements in basic skills such as vocabulary and grammar. They are more confident in using Arabic in simple contexts and High school: Students in high school show more complex development in language acquisition, especially in presentation, debate, and essay writing skills in Arabic.

Students' learning motivation also increased after implementing the PJBL. Students feel more enthusiastic because this method gives them the freedom to explore topics that are of interest and relevant to their daily lives. Students feel more interested in Arabic because the projects given are creative and challenging, such as making posters about Arabic traditions and High School: More

complex projects such as Arabic cultural studies encourage students to study more deeply and feel more motivated to achieve satisfactory results.

The PJBL method also has an impact on developing students' collaborative skills. They work together in groups to complete projects, which helps improve teamwork and problem-solving skills. Middle School: Students at this level begin to learn how to work in teams, divide tasks, and solve simple problems and High School: At the high school level, more complex projects allow students to be more involved in group discussions, planning, and decision making.

Although PJBL provides many benefits, several challenges arise in its implementation: Teachers: Some teachers still have difficulty designing projects that suit students' level of understanding. Apart from that, limited time and resources are also obstacles in implementing this method optimally. and Students: Some students, especially in junior high school, have difficulty understanding complex project instructions, so they require more intensive guidance from the teacher.

Conclusion

The application of the PJBL method in the Arabic Language Teaching Module in the Independent Curriculum in Semarang City Middle Schools and High Schools has had a positive impact on improving students' Arabic language skills, learning motivation, and collaboration and problem solving abilities. However, challenges such as teacher readiness in designing projects and time constraints need to be considered to increase the effectiveness of this method, Teacher Training: There is a need for further training for teachers so that they can design projects that are more varied and appropriate to students' a Infrastructure Support: Adequate facilities and resources must be provided by schools to support project implementation, such as access to technology and relevant teaching materials. Tiered Approach: Developing PJBL-based teaching modules that are tiered according to middle and high school levels can help overcome differences in students' abilities in completing projects. With proper implementation, PJBL in learning Arabic in the Independent Curriculum in Semarang City can be an effective method for improving the quality of foreign language learning in Indonesia.

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